

Differences in chimeric manifestations: a) almost all tillers are dwarf type with few normal tillers, b) half the tillers are dwarf, the other half normal, and c) almost all the tillers are normal with few dwarf tillers.

Phenotypes of the progenies derived from chimeric plants: d) dwarf type, e) chimeric type having both dwarf and normal tillers, and f) normal type.

F₂ segregation for plant types in the crosses involving d1 chimeric plant.^a

Cross	Segregation in F ₂				χ ²	P
	Normal	Dwarf	Chimera	Total		
Dwarf plant/IR24	47	15	0	62	0.022	0.70-0.90
IR24/dwarf plant	224	71	3	298	0.137	0.70-0.90
Dwarf plant/TC65	260	88	0	348	0.015	0.90-0.99
TC65/dwarf plant	318	94	5	417	1.049	0.30-0.50
Dwarf plant/normal plant	383	134	3	520	0.233	0.50-0.70
Normal plant/dwarf plant	259	102	0	361	2.040	0.10-0.30

^aDwarf plant = dwarf plant progenies derived from d1 chimeric rice. Normal plant = normal plant progenies derived from d1 chimeric rice. ^bN = normal, D = dwarf.

from dwarf, chimeric, and normal types were 26.7, 44.4, and 9.8%, respectively. The frequency of mutation in dwarf to normal is higher than in normal to dwarf.

Based on the results obtained from the inheritance and allelic tests, dwarf plant progenies of chimeric plants have

the *d-1* alleles while the normal progenies have the wild *D-1* alleles. We hypothesize that originally the chimeric plant had the *D-1* allele, but then the gene mutated to the recessive *d-1* allele. As a result, a chimeric plant has both dwarf (*d-1* allele) and normal tillers (*D-1* allele). If the progenies of a chi-

meric plant inherited the *d-1* allele, they become dwarf plants. If progenies inherited the *D-1* allele, they become normal plants. Throughout the growth stages of the rice plant, the *d-1* allele may revert to *D-1* allele or vice versa causing a dwarf plant to produce normal tillers and a normal plant to have dwarf tillers.

We also hypothesize that the *dl* chimeric rice plant, a very unstable mutant, occurs due to the on and off expression of the *D-1* allele, which appears to be controlled by factors such as a mutable gene, transposons, and methylation. A fine restriction fragment length polymorphism linkage map for *dl* is being developed, and we are cloning the *dl* gene to understand the mechanism of high mutation in the d1 chimeric rice plant. ■

Increasing yield potential of irrigated rice through recurrent selection

P.H.N. Rangel, F.J.P. Zimmermann, and P.C.F. Neves, Empresa Brasileira de Pesquisa Agropecuária/Centro Nacional de Pesquisa Arroz e Feijão (EMBRAPA/CNPAF), Caixa Postal 179, Goiânia, Goiás, Brazil 74001-970

Recurrent selection allows scientists to increase the frequency of favorable genotypes from a large population

through selecting and intermating generations quickly.

To assess the possibility of using this breeding method in irrigated rice in Brazil, we divided 162 S_{0.2} families (S₀ plant-derived families self-pollinated twice) into two groups (early-maturing and medium-maturing) and evaluated them in two environments. Each group was divided into two subgroups and then tested in the field with controls BR-IRGA 409 (early-maturing) and CICA 8 (medium-maturing).

The experiment was laid out in two triple-square lattices (10 × 10 m and 8 × 8 m). The S_{0.2} families came from the early-maturing population CNA-IRAT 4PR/1/1 and medium-maturing population CNA-IRAT 4ME/1/1. Individual and joint analyses of variance were done; we also estimated variance components within each maturation cycle group.

In all cases, the F test revealed highly significant differences (P<0.01) among the mean grain yields for the early- and

Average of original (Mo) and selected (Ms) populations with respective mean standard errors, and estimates of gains through direct selection on grain yield and indirect selection over the other characteristics, based on the classic selection index with a 30% selection intensity.

Characteristic	Early-maturing ^a		Medium-maturing ^a		Direct selection on grain yield (%)		Selection based on classical index (%)	
	Mo	Ms	Mo	Ms	Early-maturing	Medium-maturing	Early-maturing	Medium-maturing
Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	4.6 (±.03)	5.5 (±.03)	4.5 (±.03)	5.3 (±.03)	9.8	11.9	9.6	10.1
Days to 50% flowering	98 (±.11)	98 (±.11)	104 (±.12)	107 (±.12)	-0.1	0.1	-0.1	1.3
Panicle blast ^b score	4.5 (±.03)	4.6 (±.03)	3.8 (±.02)	3.7 (±.02)	1.2	2.6	-0.1	-1.1
Brown spot ^b score	3.8 (±.03)	3.9 (±.03)	4.1 (±.03)	3.7 (±.03)	0.2	-1.7	-0.4	-4.6

^a Mean standard error based on 983 and 981 observations for the early- and medium-maturing families, respectively. ^b Scored using the scales in the *Standard evaluation system for rice*.

medium-maturing families. The average grain yield was 4.6 t ha⁻¹ for the early-maturing families and 4.5 t ha⁻¹ for the medium-maturing families (see table). However, in the early group, six families yielded more than 6 t ha⁻¹, and in the medium group, two families yielded more than 7 t ha⁻¹. The average

of the selected families equaled 5.5 t ha⁻¹ in the early-maturing group and 5.3 t ha⁻¹ in the medium-maturing group. These findings show the possibility of positively altering the population means through recurrent selection (see table).

If families are selected (at an intensity of 30%) based only on grain yield

(direct selection), the genetic gains estimated for the cycle would be 9.8% for the early-maturing families and 11.9% for the medium-maturing families (see table). However, the indirect gain for panicle blast would be 1.2 and 2.6%, respectively for each group, demonstrating that selecting directly for grain yield increases the populations' susceptibility to the disease.

The classical index of Smith (1936) and Hazel (1943), which simultaneously considers all characters, can be used to select the best families to be recombined for initiating a new cycle of recurrent selection. Using this index, genetic gains for grain yield are similar to those obtained with direct selection with the additional advantage of simultaneously increasing (over the original populations) resistance to panicle blast and brown spot in all improved populations (see table). In the populations studied, one recurrent selection cycle was efficient for increasing grain yield. ■

Transgenic rice plants expressing rice yellow mottle virus coat protein gene

N. Kouassi, Plant Biology Division, International Laboratory for Tropical Agricultural Biotechnology The Scripps Research Institute (ILTAB/TSRI), MTC7, 10666 North Torrey Pine Road, La Jolla, CA 92037, USA; C. Brugidou, ILTAB-Institut français de recherche scientifique pour le développement en coopération (ORSTOM); L. Chen, M. Ngon A. Yassi, and R. N. Beachy, ILTAB/TSRI; C. M. Fauquet, ILTAB-ORSTOM

Coat protein-mediated resistance (CP-MR) is used to induce resistance caused by the expression of a virus coat protein (CP) gene in transgenic plants (Powell et al 1986). We investigated the use of this strategy to produce transgenic plants resistant to rice yellow mottle virus (RYMV), an important viral disease in Africa.

This virus was first reported in Kenya (Bakker 1970). The genome organization was achieved at ILTAB (Ngon A Yassi et al 1994). Transformation experiments using the biolistic method, which involves micro-projectile bombardment of embryogenic calli or immature embryos (Christou et al 1991; Li et al 1993; Sivamani et al 1996; Zhang et al 1996), followed. Four different constructs containing the cDNA sequence of the RYMV coat protein gene were inserted into the ubiquitin promoter-Nos terminator cassette and engineered in different ways to produce the CP (CP+), a truncated coat protein (CPΔNTS), a RNA sense (mRNA), and a RNA antisense (CP-). The biolistic method was used to introduce these into embryogenic calli of japonica rice variety Taipei 309. We obtained a relatively high transformation efficiency (see table).

Cotransformation with various ratios (gene of selection/gene of interest) was achieved using the different CP chimeric plasmids and the plasmid pMON410 carrying the hygromycin resistance gene. After several rounds of selection on hygromycin, the plantlets were transferred to soil. Molecular analysis was performed using DNA extracted from leaves of putative R₀ transgenic plants following the method. We amplified by polymerase chain reaction (PCR) the *hph* gene and the entire cassette containing the gene of interest (ubiquitin-CP-Nos=3000 bp). Southern blot experiments using a CP probe ³²P radio-labeled were also performed and confirmed the integration of the gene in R₀ plants (see figure).

We tested 117 transgenic lines and all were found to carry the *hph* gene, while an average percentage (62%) of independent R₀ lines were positive by both